

The Relation Between Time of Coagulation and Electrolyte Concentration

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Mechanism of coagulation of negatively charged iron oxide sol has been studied. Attempts have been made to verify the Bhattacharya's equation relating the time of coagulation and the concentration of the coagulant.

Extensive studies have been made on the coagulation of colloids and attempts have been made to explain the mechanism of rapid and slow coagulation. Coagulation is considered as a rapid process when the coagulation time is about 5 to 7 seconds. In such cases, single constant coagulation values are obtained. On the other hand, on addition of smaller quantities of electrolyte, one may obtain the phenomenon of slow coagulation. According to Zsigmondy, in the region of rapid coagulation, the micelles are completely discharged and they stick together¹. Zsigmondy derived an equation,²

$$\theta = \frac{1}{Kv_0} = \frac{1}{4Dr\nu_0}$$

where ν_0 is the original number of particles. r is the radius of sphere of attraction and D is the diffusion constant. Slow coagulation on the other hand is a much more complicated process. It may be autocatalytic in character, coagulation-time curve being S shaped. In slow coagulation, the extent of coagulation is such that the micelles are partially discharged but it is still at some distance from isoelectric point. Determination of slow coagulation value is therefore much more complicated.

Mathews and Murphy³, Boutaric,⁴ Dumanskii and Scherschnev⁵ investigated the relation between the electrolyte concentration and time of coagulation which may be expressed as $t=ac^n$. Bhattacharya and Co-workers⁶ studied the variation of time of coagulation with the electrolyte concentration in number of colloidal systems and derived the following equation.

$$C = a + \frac{m \cdot \frac{1}{t}}{n + \frac{1}{t}} \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{1}{C-a} = \frac{nt}{m} + \frac{1}{m}$$

Where a , m and n are constants. Attempts were made to verify the above equation. Experiments were performed with two different concentrations of sols of negatively charged iron oxide sols, viz., E and 3E/4, using different electrolytes. The results are given in Tables 1 & 2.

TABLE 1—COAGULATION VALUE IN MILLIMOLES PER LITRE CORRESPONDING TO TIME OF COAGULATION.

Sol E : Fe₂O₃ = 2.50 g./l. Sucrose = 1.2% Ammonia } Trace & Chloride } pH = 7.6

Conc. in mM/litre (C)	Electrolyte Time in minutes	KCl 1/t	a = 122	
			C - a	1/C - a
140	92	0.0108	18	0.0555
150	47	0.0212	28	0.0357
160	35	0.0285	38	0.0263
170	20	0.0500	48	0.0208
180	12	0.0833	58	0.0172
190	6	0.1666	68	0.0147
			a = 1.125	
1.25	61	0.0164	0.0125	8.000
1.30	40	0.0250	0.175	5.715
1.35	24	0.0416	0.225	4.444
1.40	12	0.0833	0.275	3.637
1.45	7	0.1420	0.325	3.077
			a = 0.687	
0.725	63	0.0158	0.038	26.31
0.750	30	0.0333	0.063	15.87
0.775	16	0.0625	0.088	11.36
0.800	9	0.1110	0.113	8.85
0.825	5	0.2000	0.138	7.24

TABLE 2—COAGULATION VALUE IN MILLIMOLES PER LITRE CORRESPONDING TO TIME OF COAGULATION

Sol 3 E/4

Conc. in mM/litre (C)	Electrolyte Time in minutes	KCl 1/t	a = 96	
			C - a	1/C - a
110	79	0.0126	14	0.0714
120	40	0.0250	24	0.0416
130	25	0.0400	34	0.0294
140	18	0.0555	44	0.0227
150	10	0.1000	54	0.0183
160	5	0.2000	64	0.0156
			a = 1.025	
1.10	75	0.0133	0.075	13.33
1.15	63	0.0158	0.125	8.00
1.20	40	0.0250	0.175	5.715
1.25	25	0.0400	0.225	4.444
1.30	12	0.0833	0.275	3.637
1.35	5	0.2000	0.325	3.087
			a = 0.625	
0.650	58	0.0172	0.025	40.0
0.675	35	0.0285	0.050	20.0
0.700	22	0.0454	0.075	13.3
0.725	12	0.0833	0.100	10.0

Discussion

The process of coagulation involves two distinct phenomena (a) complete or partial neutralization of charge to a critical value⁷ and (b) coalescence of the particles until they become large enough to settle down. The former is an instantaneous process while the latter takes time depending upon the concentration of electrolyte, etc. Studies in slow coagulation may throw some light on coagulation process. In the present work attempts have been made to apply Bhattacharya's equation⁸ to the variation of time of coagulation with electrolyte concentration. Bhattacharya's equation is as follows.

$$C = a + \frac{m \cdot \frac{1}{t}}{n + 1/t}$$

where a, m, and n are constants. 'a' is the limiting concentration below which coagulation is not possible, 'm' represents excess of electrolyte added above the critical concentration to cause immediate coagulation; 'n' is constant which is the characteristic of the sol and is connected with the sensitivity of the sol to the electrolyte. The data are given in Tables 1 and 2.

The graphs of $\frac{1}{c-a}$ against t and c against t can be

constructed to obtain the values of 'a', 'm' and 'n'. Table 3 summarizes the values of 'a', 'm' and 'n'.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF CONSTANTS a, m AND n

Electrolyte used	a		m		n Min ⁻¹	
	mM/l		mM/l			
	E	3E/4	E	3E/4	E	3E/4
KCl	122	96	90.9	83.3	0.054	0.062
BaCl ₂	1.12	1.05	4.0	3.8	0.32	0.30
AlCl ₃	0.68	0.62	0.2	0.16	0.095	0.066

With dilution of the sol, 'a' and 'm' decrease i. e. less of the electrolyte is required to coagulate dilute sols.

This behaviour is similar in all the three electrolytes with monovalent, bivalent and trivalent ions. This is similar to the results obtained by Bhattacharya, where 'a' and 'm' decrease regularly. Variation of 'n' appears to be of an anomalous character. Thus in our case, 'n' increases with monovalent ion, remains almost constant in case of bivalent ion and decreases in case of trivalent ion, while in the case of Bhattacharya, 'n' increases in monovalent ion but decreases both in cases of bivalent and trivalent ions.

The coagulation of colloids involves two distinct processes—neutralization of charge and subsequent coalescence of the particles so that they become large enough to settle down. The first is obviously a process depending entirely on charge. Hence, one may take 'a' as the concentration of the electrolyte required to neutralize the charge or to bring it to a definite minimum value. The interpretation of 'm' and 'n' are difficult. If 't' is infinitesimally small $C - a = m$, i. e. $a + m$ represents the concentration required for rapid coagulation. 'n' cannot be easily interpreted. It is doubtful whether equation of this type serve any useful purpose.

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